

The Impact of Passive Displacement Fixed Jaw Design on Liner Wear in Single Toggle Jaw Crushers

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ABSTRACT:

Single toggle jaw crushers are widely used in mining and aggregate industries, but they suffer from significant liner wear, leading to increased maintenance costs and downtime. This research investigates the impact of a novel single toggle jaw crusher design with a passive displacement fixed jaw on liner wear. The investigation was done by carrying out a comparative analysis between the conventional jaw crusher design and the new jaw crusher design. During the evaluation of the conventional and new crusher designs, the liners were initially weighed with an electronic scale of 20 g sensitivity, and the readings were recorded. The jaw liners were then assembled to the crusher jaws before starting the crusher. Measured rock samples were then loaded intermittently into the crushing chamber to be crushed. The jaw liners were dismantled from the crusher and weighed, after crushing 470.50 kg of rock sample. The wear of the jaw liners was computed by subtracting their final weights from their initial weights. A total of 1411.5 kg of rocks were crushed with each crusher design configuration. After testing the crusher for both the conventional and the new designs, the results show that the overall wear amount experienced by the conventional jaw crusher liners was 87.88 % more than that of the new crusher design. This revealed that the introduction of a passive movable fixed jaw helped in reducing the relative sliding between the jaw liners and the crushed material, hence the reduction in jaw liner wear.

Keywords: Liner wear, jaw crusher, minning industry, crusher design.

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INTRODUCTION

Single toggle jaw crushers (illustrated in Figure 1) are widely used in the mining and aggregate industries, but they suffer from significant liner wear, leading to increased maintenance costs and

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downtime. The high maintenance costs associated with replacing worn parts in crushing equipment underscore the importance of researching crushing processes [1].

Figure 1. Illustration of Single Toggle Jaw Crusher
Source: [2]

The main objective of this article was to investigate the impact of a newly developed single toggle jaw crusher with passive displacement fixed jaw on jaw liner wear. By comparing the wear performance of this innovative design with traditional single toggle jaw crushers, this research seeks to identify potential improvements in crusher efficiency and durability.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Wear in Crushing Equipment

Wear refers to the progressive damage or material loss from a solid surface due to relative motion with another substance [3]. It arises from complex mechanical, physical, and chemical interactions, with key mechanisms including abrasive, adhesive, fatigue, fretting, erosion, oxidation, and corrosion wear [4]. Among these, abrasive wear is particularly significant, especially in crushing equipment, accounting for approximately 80-90% of the total wear [4,5].

Abrasive Wear in Single Toggle Jaw Crushers

Abrasive wear is defined as wear due to hard particles or hard protuberances forced against and moving along a solid surface [5,6]. Natural rocks, being hard and brittle, require high compressive or impact forces to fracture. This creates a severe wear environment for counterfaces, which often include phases softer than the mineral phases of the rocks [7].

It has been established that due to the high level of relative sliding that occurs at the contact interfaces between the crushed rocks and the jaw liners, the jaw liners experience a high amount of abrasive wear [8, 1,9,10].

Wear Measurement in Single Toggle Jaw Crushers

The extent of wear in jaw crusher liners can be quantitatively assessed by measuring the mass of the jaw liner specimens before and after testing. The mass differences correspond to the material loss due to wear, thereby providing an objective evaluation of wear severity [1,11].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of New Design

To minimize the sliding interaction between the particles and the liner, the jaw crusher has been redesigned to incorporate a passively moving fixed jaw that can move vertically under the influence

of the swing jaw and the crushed material. This fixed jaw, facilitated by a sliding plate, is designed to slide within a guide mechanism integrated into the main frame of the crusher.

Figure 2. Passive Displacement Fixed Jaw Configuration for the New Crusher Design

At its lower end, the passive displacement fixed jaw is equipped with a spring-loading system, which aids the sliding plate in returning to its initial position after being displaced downward by the action of the swing jaw and the crushed material. The mechanism governing the operation of the movable fixed jaw is illustrated in Figure 2.

In order to compare the liner wear rate of the passive moving jaw design with that of the traditional fixed jaw design, the fixed jaw has been designed to be easily modified to mimic the traditional fixed jaw design.

Figure 3. Fixed Jaw Configuration for Conventional Design

The modification was achieved by simply replacing the springs under the sliding plate with metallic bushings as illustrated in Figure 3. The metallic bushings, by providing a stable and secure locking mechanism, replicate the conditions under which a conventional fixed jaw operates, ensuring that the wear patterns closely resemble real-working scenarios.

The newly developed single toggle jaw crusher used for the experiment is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 4. Newly Developed Single Toggle Jaw Crusher Used for the Experiment

Testing and Comparative Analysis of New and Conventional Single Toggle Jaw Crushers

Figure 5 illustrate the procedure employed in evaluating the wear performance of the jaw liners in the new and the conventional jaw crusher configurations. During the evaluation, a total of 2823 kg of rocks were crushed; 1411.5 kg for each crusher design configuration (conventional and new). The crushing was repeated three times at an amount of 470.5 kg per section under similar operating condition. The jaw liners were dismantled from the crusher jaw and were weighed after each section.

Figure 5. Methods Used in Evaluating the Jaw Liners

The rock samples used in the evaluation were obtained from three different mining sites at Tarkwa to represent a variety of geological conditions. The second crushing round, dolomite rocks was used for both configurations of the crusher. Whilst, quartzite rocks were used for the first and third rounds. This approach helps to provide a comprehensive understanding of the crusher's performance.

Before starting any crushing operations, the jaw liners were weighed. This step involves carefully measuring the mass of each liner individually using an electronic scale. The electronic scale used has a sensitivity of 20 g and a weighing capacity of 100 kg. This initial measurement serves as a baseline to track any changes in liner mass over time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Wear Analysis of the Fixed and Swing Jaw Liners for the Conventional Design and the New Design

It was discovered that the wear pattern on the jaw liners in the crushing chamber was more pronounced at the bottom section compared to other parts within the chamber, as shown in Figure 6. This observation was consistent with the findings of Shyam [8].

Figure 6 Appearance of Jaw Liners after Crushing Rocks

Figure 7 shows the effect of the amount of crushed rocks on the mass of the jaw swing jaw liners for both the conventional design and the new design. The graph indicates that both designs exhibit a negative correlation between the mass of crushed rock and the mass of swing jaw liner. This

suggests that as the amount of crushed rocks increases, the swing jaw liners for both designs progressively decrease in mass.

Figure 7. Amount of Rock Crushed and the Corresponding Reduction in Mass of the Fixed Jaw Liner

The sharp drop in the graph at the initial stage can be attributed to the high abrasiveness of the rocks crushed at these stages. The new design however, consistently demonstrates a lower mass of swing jaw liner loss across all levels of crushed rock mass, making it a better choice for the two design configurations.

In fact, the wear measured in the swing jaw liner for the conventional and new jaw crusher designs were 144.44% and 20% more than their respective fixed jaw liners. This indicates that the sliding interaction on the fixed jaw was less compared to that of the swing jaw liner. Also, the percentage wear values show that the new design allowed for a reduced relative motion between the swing and fixed jaw liners.

Figure 8. Amount of Rock Crushed and the Corresponding Reduction in Mass of the Swing Jaw Liner

The graph shown in Figure 8, illustrates the relationship between the mass of crushed rock processed and the mass of fixed jaw liners for conventional and new crusher designs. As shown in the graph, both the conventional and new designs exhibit a negative correlation between the mass of crushed rock and the mass of the jaw liner. This indicates that as more rock is crushed, the mass of the jaw liner decreases due to wear. The slope of each line represents the wear rate of the jaw liner. A steeper slope suggests a higher rate of wear.

The conventional design demonstrates a relatively steeper slope, indicating a higher wear rate. This suggests that the conventional design may require more frequent liner replacements. The new design, on the other hand, exhibits a flatter slope, suggesting a lower wear rate. This can be attributed to incorporation of passive movable fixed jaw liner, which reduces the sliding interaction between the jaw liners and the crushed material [12].

The graph shown in Figure 9 shows the effect of the amount of crushed rocks on the total material worn from the jaw liners (both the swing and fixed jaw) for conventional and the new crusher design. Both designs exhibit a positive correlation between the mass of crushed rocks and the total mass of liner material loss. This suggests that as the amount of crushed rocks increases, the liner material loss also tends to increase. However, the new design consistently demonstrates a lower total mass of liner material loss across all levels of crushed rock mass. This provides strong evidence in support of the hypothesis that the incorporation of a passive movable fixed jaw can reduce the wear rate of the jaw liners.

The new design is more efficient in retaining liner material by 87.88% compared to the conventional design. A reduction in liner material loss can lead to significant cost savings over time. This is particularly important as the jaw crusher will require less frequent liner replacement or maintenance.

Figure 9. Total Liner Material Loss the corresponding Amount of Rock Crushed

The cumulative wear experienced by the fixed jaw liners for both the conventional and new crusher designs were less compared to the swing jaw liners. This observation contradicts the usual wear pattern in single toggle jaw crushers as established by Lindqvist and Evertsson [10] and Machado *et al.* [13], that the swing jaw liner wears more than the fixed jaw liner. This contradiction can be due to nip angle settings of the crushers used in their experiment, which was not stated in the articles published.

CONCLUSIONS

The wear measured in the swing jaw liner for the conventional and new jaw, crusher designs were 144.44% and 20% more than their fixed jaw liner counterparts respectively. This indicates that the sliding interaction on the fixed jaw was less compared to that of the swing jaw liner.

The innovative new design resulted in a substantial reduction in jaw liner wear, as evidenced by an 87.88% decrease in wear compared to the conventional design.

By incorporating a passive moving fixed jaw into the crusher design, the relative slippage between the jaw liners and the crushed material has been significantly reduced, resulting in a lower liner wear rate for the new design.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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